

Magnetic and Spectroscopic Studies on some New Bis- and Tris-complexes of Iron(II) with 3,5-Dimethyl-1-(2'-pyridyl)pyrazole : Indication of 5T_2 — 1A_1 Equilibrium

NITYANANDA SAHA* and SUSANTA K. KAR

Department of Chemistry, University of Calcutta, 92 A. P. C. Road, Calcutta-700 009

The synthesis and physicochemical characterisation (including magnetic measurements over a temperature range and Mössbauer spectra) of a host of bis- and tris-iron(II) complexes with the title ligand, viz. 3,5-dimethyl-1-(2'-pyridyl)pyrazole (DPyPz) are reported. The bis-complexes $Fe(DPyPz)_2X_n \cdot nH_2O$ ($X=Cl, Br, NCS$; $n=0, 2$) are clearly of high-spin type ($\mu_{eff}=5.00-5.40$ B.M. at 298 K) with temperature-independent magnetic moment values, whereas the bis-perchlorate, the tris-perchlorate and the tris-iodide species show intermediate magnetic moment values ($\mu_{eff}=2.56$ and 2.28 B.M. respectively at 293 K) which have been rationalised in terms of 5T_2 — 1A_1 equilibrium. The diffuse reflectance spectra of all the iron(II) complexes are indicative of ${}^5T_{2g}$ — 5E_g transition in an octahedral environment. An approximate octahedral configuration around iron(II) nucleus has also been ascertained from the values of isomeric shift and quadrupole splitting of ${}^{57}Fe$ Mössbauer spectrum of a representative complex. Ir data point out the pyrazolyl and the pyridine nitrogens of the title ligand as the bonding sites when complexed with iron(II); the counterions (X) are mostly coordinated in the bis-species while the same retain their ionic character in the tris-complexes.

THE importance of pyrazole (1:2 diazole) derivatives in relevance to bio-systems has initiated substantial research in the field of coordination chemistry using pyrazole-derived ligands during nearly the last two decades. The fact has been well-authenticated by a recent review by Trofimenko¹, which also includes significant work from our laboratory. In view of well-documented interesting magnetic and spectroscopic properties of iron(II) complexes with bidentate (N—N) donor ligands², we report here, in continuation of our recent work^{3,4} of pyrazole-derived ligands, the synthesis and physicochemical characterisation of a number of new iron(II) complexes of the title ligand (DPyPz) (Fig. 1).

[DPyPz]
Fig. 1.

Experimental

The ligand, 3,5-dimethyl-1-(2'-pyridyl)pyrazole was synthesised by the condensation of acetylacetone and 2-hydrazinopyridine and distilled in the pure state (b.p. 74°/0.4 mm Hg) and characterised by elemental analyses, ir and nmr spectral data

as described earlier⁵. All operations in connection with the preparation of the iron(II) complexes were carried out under dry nitrogen due to well-known air-sensitivity of iron(II) salts. In each preparation, prior to the actual interaction with the ligand, solutions of iron(II) salts used were treated with iron powder to reduce traces of iron(III), if any, in the starting materials.

[$Fe(DPyPz)_2Cl_2$]: A solution of anhydrous iron(II) chloride (0.002 mol, 0.25 g) in methanol (50 ml) was added to the ligand DPyPz (0.004 mol, 0.7 g) dissolved in the same solvent (50 ml). The resulting deep red solution was heated at water-bath temperature for ~10 min and then concentrated under reduced pressure. On cooling the concentrated solution in an ice-bath, an orange-red shining microcrystalline compound separated out immediately. The compound was filtered off, washed several times with cold methanol and then once with ice-cold water and finally dried under reduced pressure over silica gel.

[$Fe(DPyPz)_2Br_2$]. $2H_2O$ and [$Fe(DPyPz)_2(SCN)_2$]: The complexes were prepared by refluxing an ethanolic solution of the chloride complex (prepared above) with a saturated solution of the ammonium salt of the corresponding anion. Upon concentration and cooling, the desired coloured complex in each case separated out and collected as before.

[$Fe(DPyPz)_2(ClO_4)_2$]. $2H_2O$: Aqueous solutions (20 ml) of $FeSO_4 \cdot 7H_2O$ (0.002 mol, 0.55 g) and $Ba(ClO_4)_2$ (0.003 mol, 1 g) were mixed with stirring. The precipitated barium sulphate was filtered

through sintered glass filter and the filtrate was directly run into methanolic solution (30 ml) of the ligand. A pale red microcrystalline compound immediately separated, which was washed with water and collected as before.

$[Fe(DPyPz)_3](ClO_4)_2$: The tris-iron(II) perchlorate complex was prepared by a similar method as described above by reacting the iron(II) salt with the ligand in 1 : 3 mole proportions.

$[Fe(DPyPz)_3]I_2$: The resulting deep red solution obtained by interaction of methanolic solution of anhydrous iron(II) chloride (0.002 mol, 0.25 g) with a solution of the ligand (0.006 mol, 1.1 g) in the same solvent, was allowed to react with a saturated solution of potassium iodide. The mixed solution was concentrated under pressure and then cooled in an ice-bath when an orange-red crystalline compound separated out, which was filtered off and collected as before.

The iron content of the complexes was analysed by standard volumetric methods. C, H and N were estimated microanalytically at C.D.R.I., Lucknow. Halogen content was estimated as silver halide by the usual methods. Physicochemical measurements were carried out as described earlier⁵ unless otherwise stated. The magnetic susceptibility measurements in the temperature range 83–293 K or even

to 373 K were made on a Newport variable temperature Gouy balance using mercury tetrathiocyanato cobalt(II) standard at the University of New South Wales, Australia; and Mössbauer spectrum was recorded in the same University with a spectrometer operating in the time mode equipped with a room temperature co-source in a palladium matrix and calibrated with metallic iron foil. Isomer shifts are quoted on the nitroprusside scale.

Results and Discussion

Based on analytical data, the stoichiometric formulae of the reported iron(II) complexes are given in Table 1, together with elemental analyses and other physical data. In spite of our best efforts, conductivity measurements on the complexes could not be carried out due to rapid and extensive solvolysis of the species on dissolution in a solvent.

The results of magnetic susceptibility measurements (in terms of effective magnetic moment values) on the polycrystalline varieties of the present iron(II) complexes between 83 and 293 K are contained in Table 2. The results clearly show that the bis-chelates, $[Fe(DPyPz)_2Cl_2]$, $[Fe(DPyPz)_2Br_2] \cdot 2H_2O$ and $[Fe(DPyPz)_2(SCN)_2]$ are magnetically normal high-spin compounds and the magnetic

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND MAGNETIC MOMENT DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Compd.*	Colour	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)					μ_{eff}^{**} B.M.
		C	H	N	Fe	Anion	
$[Fe(DPyPz)_2Cl_2]$	Orange red	50.52 (50.76)	4.35 (4.65)	17.90 (17.76)	11.70 (11.81)	14.62 (15.01)	4.99
$[Fe(DPyPz)_2Br_2] \cdot 2H_2O$	Greenish yellow	39.82 (40.14)	4.07 (4.35)	14.32 (14.05)	9.12 (9.34)	26.85 (26.76)	5.34
$[Fe(DPyPz)_2(SCN)_2]$	Yellow	50.51 (50.98)	4.01 (4.25)	22.15 ^a (21.62)	10.52 (10.78)	—	5.43
$[Fe(DPyPz)_2(ClO_4)_2] \cdot 2H_2O$	Pale red	37.35 (37.77)	3.82 (4.08)	12.85 (13.20)	8.50 (8.76)	10.75 ^b (11.15)	2.45
$[Fe(DPyPz)_2](ClO_4)_2$	Red	46.32 (46.52)	4.10 (4.26)	16.02 (16.28)	7.12 (7.21)	8.90 ^b (9.17)	2.57
$[Fe(DPyPz)_3]I_2$	Orange red	43.15 (43.43)	3.68 (3.98)	14.82 (15.20)	6.42 (6.73)	30.31 (30.64)	3.30

*DPyPz = one molecule of the ligand (C₁₀H₁₁N₃). **At 298 K. ^aIncluding nitrogen present in thiocyanate. ^bChlorine present in the perchlorate.

TABLE 2—EFFECTIVE MAGNETIC MOMENT VALUES (μ_{eff} , B.M.) OF THE COMPLEXES* AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

Temp. K	$[FeL_2Cl_2]$	$[FeL_2Br_2] \cdot 2H_2O$	$[FeL_2(SCN)_2]$	$[FeL_2(ClO_4)_2] \cdot 2H_2O$	$[FeL_2](ClO_4)_2 \cdot 2H_2O$	$[FeL_3]I_2$
373	4.97	5.31	5.43	—	—	3.35
353	4.95	5.33	5.42	—	—	2.97
313	4.98	5.31	5.42	—	—	2.54
293	4.90	5.31 [†]	5.42	2.42	2.56	2.28
273	4.90	5.34	5.41	2.01	2.23	2.20
263	4.90	5.32	5.40	1.77	2.08	2.16
233	4.90	5.30	5.40	1.63	1.73	2.08
203	4.90	5.28	5.41	1.54	1.53	2.06
173	4.89	5.28	5.39	1.46	1.43	2.03
143	4.87	5.26	5.37	1.37	1.37	2.02
113	4.82	5.22	5.27	1.18	1.31	1.99
83	4.77	5.15	5.03	1.14	1.26	1.94

*L = DPyPz

moment values ($\mu_{\text{eff}} \sim 4.90 - 5.42$ B.M. at 293 K) are temperature-independent. However, the bis-perchlorate $[\text{Fe}(\text{DPyPz})_2(\text{ClO}_4)_2] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and the tris-chelates $[\text{Fe}(\text{DPyPz})_3]\text{X}_3$ ($\text{X} = \text{ClO}_4$ and I) have magnetic moment values ($\mu_{\text{eff}} \sim 2.3 - 2.57$ B.M. at 293 K) intermediate between those observed for high-spin ($\mu_{\text{eff}} \sim 5.3$ B.M.) and low-spin ($\mu_{\text{eff}} = 0$) iron(II) species. It is well-established that the magnetic moments of iron(II) complexes with ${}^5T_{2g}$ ($\mu_{\text{eff}} \sim 5.30$ B.M.) or ${}^3T_{2g}$ ($\mu_{\text{eff}} \sim 3.9$ B.M.) ground state terms are independent of temperature. In the present studies, the bis-chelates $[\text{Fe}(\text{DPyPz})_2]\text{X}_2 \cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O}$ ($\text{X} = \text{Cl}, \text{Br}, \text{SCN}$) exhibit normal magnetic behaviour over the temperature range 373–83 K (Table 2) indicating a ${}^5T_{2g}$ ground state in the species. However, magnetic moments of the bis- and tris-perchlorate and tris-iodide iron(II) complexes fall continuously with the decrease in temperature (Table 2, Figs. 2a and 2b); a closer scrutiny will, however, show that the rate of decrease of magnetic moments becomes less as the temperature is lowered. This type of magnetic behaviour can be reconciled in terms of either anti-ferromagnetic interaction between neighbouring iron atoms or a thermal equilibrium involving terms of different spin multiplicities. The reported iron(II) complexes of 3,5-dimethyl-1-(2'-pyridyl)-pyrazole having the same donor sites as the iron(II) complexes of 2-(2'-pyridyl)imidazole⁶, are thought to have no significant Fe–Fe interactions in the species. The most reasonable explanation for such magnetic behaviour is, therefore, that there is a thermal equilibrium between the high-spin and low-spin states.

Diffuse reflectance spectra: The room temperature reflectance spectra of the reported spin-free bis-iron(II) complexes, viz. $[\text{Fe}(\text{DPyPz})_2]\text{X}_2 \cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O}$ ($\text{X} = \text{Cl}, \text{Br}$ and SCN), are characterised by a broad band around $11\,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ which may be assigned to ${}^5T_{2g} \rightarrow {}^5E_g$ transition⁷ in an octahedral field; this band corresponds to $10Dq$. It is required that

Fig. 2a. Variation of magnetic moments μ_{eff} with temperature for (Δ) $[\text{Fe}(\text{DPyPz})_2](\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, ($\bullet$) $[\text{Fe}(\text{DPyPz})_2](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ and ($\circ$) $[\text{Fe}(\text{DPyPz})_2]\text{I}_2$.

Fig. 2b. Variation of χ_M with temperature for (Δ) $[\text{Fe}(\text{DPyPz})_2]\text{I}_2$, ($\bullet$) $[\text{Fe}(\text{DPyPz})_2](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ and ($\circ$) $[\text{Fe}(\text{DPyPz})_2](\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

$10Dq$ should be almost equal to the spin-pairing energy π^0 (where $\pi = 2.5B + 4C \approx 18.5B$, $C \approx 4B$, the terms having their usual significance). In the present studies taking $10Dq = \pi$, the B value comes to approximately 600 cm^{-1} ; the nephelauxetic ratio (β) shows a value of 0.6. A decrease in β from the normal value suggests partial covalent character of M–L bond⁸. The spectra also show two strong absorption bands around $\sim 18\,000$ and $\sim 22\,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ which may be of charge transfer origin. The species $[\text{Fe}(\text{DPyPz})_2](\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $[\text{Fe}(\text{DPyPz})_3]\text{X}_3$ ($\text{X} = \text{ClO}_4, \text{I}$) exhibit in their spectra two very strong CT bands appearing around $\sim 18\,000$ and $22\,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$. A comparatively low intensity band around $11\,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ appears as a very broad envelope on the low energy side of the main CT band, and in absence of spectral data at liquid nitrogen temperature, it is considered to be a combination of ${}^5T_{2g} \rightarrow {}^5E_g$ (H.S. type) and ${}^1A_1 \rightarrow {}^3T_1$ transitions (L.S. type) in line with spectral features of $\text{Fe}(\text{Phen})_2(\text{NCS})_2$ at 298 and $\sim 77\text{ K}$. Electronic spectral data in solution could not be recorded due to appreciable solvolysis occurring on dissolution of the complex species in a solvent.

Mössbauer spectra: The chemical isomer shifts $\delta_{\text{L.S.}}$ ($-$) 0.68 and ($-$) 0.74 mm s^{-1} at 300 and 80 K respectively) on sodium nitroprusside scale and ΔE_Q (0.35 mm s^{-1} at 300 and 80 K) for a representative iron(II) complex, $[\text{Fe}(\text{DPyPz})_2](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ (Figs. 3a and 3b) are within the range of values for low-spin iron(II) complexes in which (N–N) bidentate ligands are directly bonded to iron atom and spatial distribution around iron atom is approximately octahedral¹⁰.

Fig. 3a. Mössbauer spectrum at room temperature (300 K).

Fig. 3b. Mossbauer spectrum at 80 K.

Ir spectra: The strong ir band appearing at $1\ 575\ \text{cm}^{-1}$ which may be assigned due to $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{C}}$ and $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{N}}$ in the uncomplexed ligand has been found to shift to the higher frequency region of $\sim 1\ 600\ \text{cm}^{-1}$ in the reported iron(II) complexes indicating indirectly the participation of the ring nitrogen(s) in complexation to the iron(II) atom¹¹.

The ir spectra of $[\text{Fe}(\text{DPyPz})_2\text{Cl}_2]$ and $[\text{Fe}(\text{DPyPz})_2\text{Br}_2] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ recorded down to $250\ \text{cm}^{-1}$ show distinct bands in the region $415\text{--}425\ \text{cm}^{-1}$ which may be taken to be an indication of the participation of pyridine ring nitrogen in complex formation since there is a positive shift of this band from the position of $405\ \text{cm}^{-1}$ (assignable to pyridine ring vibration) appearing in the free ligand¹². The ir spectrum of $[\text{Fe}(\text{DPyPz})_2\text{Cl}_2]$ shows a strong band at $260\ \text{cm}^{-1}$ which may be assigned due to $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{Fe}-\text{Cl})$ ¹³ indicating the coordinated nature of the chloride ion.

The ir spectrum of high-spin $[\text{Fe}(\text{DPyPz})_2(\text{NCS})_2]$ recorded down to $200\ \text{cm}^{-1}$ on CsI phase shows distinct bands at 250 and $220\ \text{cm}^{-1}$ (which are absent in free ligand) and may be justifiably assigned to $\nu_{\text{Fe}-\text{NCS}}$ and $\nu_{\text{Fe}-\text{N}(\text{ring})}$ respectively in accordance with reported data for $\text{Fe}(\text{Phen})(\text{NCS})_2$ ¹⁴.

In the bis-perchlorate complex, the ir band of the perchlorate group due to Cl-O stretching frequency at about $1\ 100\ \text{cm}^{-1}$ is split into three components, viz. $1\ 160$, $1\ 120$ and $1\ 050\ \text{cm}^{-1}$. The extent of splitting suggests monodentate nature of perchlorate group¹⁵. The tris-perchlorate, however, shows very strong ir band covering the region $1\ 140\text{--}1\ 030\ \text{cm}^{-1}$ which is indicative of non-coordinated¹⁵ nature of the perchlorate group as expected in $[\text{FeN}_6]^{2+}$ species.

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